

**MINISTRY OF EDUCATION AND TRAINING
HO CHI MINH CITY UNIVERSITY OF LAW
FACULTY OF LEGAL LANGUAGES**

**THE EFFECT OF THEMATIC CLUSTERING ON
STUDENTS' VOCABULARY RECOGNITION AND
PRODUCTION: A SINGLE-SUBJECT RESEARCH**

A thesis submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for
the degree of Bachelor of Arts

Submitted by Ngo Nhat Thanh Tra

Supervised by Ms. Le Nguyen Thao Thy (MA.)

Ho Chi Minh City, June 21st, 2023.

STATEMENT OF AUTHORSHIP

I certify that this thesis entitled “**The effect of thematic clustering on students’ studying vocabulary recognition and production: a single-subject research**” is my own work.

Except where reference is made in the text of the thesis, this thesis does not contain material published elsewhere or extracted in whole or in part from a thesis by which I have qualified for or been awarded another degree or diploma.

No other person’s work has been used without due acknowledgement in the main text of the thesis.

This thesis has not been submitted for the award of any degree or diploma in any other tertiary institution.

Copyright is owned by the Author of the thesis.

Ho Chi Minh City, June 21st, 2023

Ngo Nhat Thanh Tra

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I would like to express my appreciation and deeply-felt words to all those concerned in my thesis.

I would like to express my sincere appreciation and gratitude for my academic supervisor, Ms. Le Nguyen Thao Thy for her endless support and care about my studies throughout the years I have spent at Ho Chi Minh City University of Law. Her informative comments and helpful instructions were a great support for me to complete this thesis.

My thanks and appreciations go to WESET English Center for their agreement and non-stop support for me to complete this work. Also, my gratitude and appreciation go to my IELTS supervisor: Mr. To Minh Dat, my CE supervisors: Mr. Nguyen Hoang Thanh and Ms. Dang Nguyen Nha Uyen at WESET English Center for their supportive and willingness to help me achieve my goals.

My sincere thanks go to my dear students at WESET English Center for their voluntariness and help in collecting the data for this study, without them it would be impossible to complete this thesis.

ABSTRACT

Together with the contrast between interference hypothesis and distinctiveness hypothesis, the decision of whether to teach vocabulary using semantic clustering, thematic clustering or other types of word clustering presents as a controversial matter. Though previous studies have already examined this issue on several perspectives, little or no evidence approached from the viewpoint of non-native speakers of English. Therefore, supporting the distinctiveness hypothesis, the study compares the effect of studying thematic clustering and unrelated clustering vocabulary on memory recognition and retention. Utilizing experiment research, a single-subject study was conducted on 6 participants throughout the course of studying, testing and interviews. The results emphasized the effectiveness of thematic clustering on vocabulary recognition and production, whilst confirming the participants' preference and positive attitudes toward this type of clustering. The study, thus, retained the distinctiveness hypothesis effect of presenting and practicing thematically related vocabulary in a non-English speaking classroom environment.

Keywords: thematic clustering; vocabulary; recognition; retention.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

STATEMENT OF AUTHORSHIP	II
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	III
ABSTRACT.....	IV
TABLE OF CONTENTS	V
LIST OF FIGURES	VIII
LIST OF TABLES	IX
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS	X
CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION.....	1
1.1 RATIONALE OF THE STUDY.....	1
1.2 STATEMENT OF PURPOSE.....	3
1.3 RESEARCH HYPOTHESES	3
1.4 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY	4
1.5 OVERVIEW OF THE THESIS CHAPTERS	4
CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW	6
2.1 RELEVANT THEORIES	6
2.1.1 <i>Thematic clustering</i>	6
2.1.2 <i>Schemata theory</i>	7
2.1.3 <i>Distinctiveness hypothesis</i>	8
2.2 PREVIOUS STUDIES	11
CHAPTER 3: METHODOLOGY	16
3.1 RESEARCH DESIGN	16
3.2 RESEARCH INSTRUMENTS	18
3.2.1 <i>Vocabulary Item</i>	18
3.2.2 <i>Tests</i>	19
3.2.2.1 <i>Immediate Tests</i>	19
3.2.2.2 <i>Delayed Tests</i>	20
3.2.3 <i>Interviews</i>	20
3.2.3.1 <i>Pre-interviews</i>	20
3.2.3.2 <i>Post-interviews</i>	21
3.2.4 <i>Observations</i>	21
3.3 PARTICIPANTS	21

3.4 RESEARCH PROCEDURE	22
3.4.1 <i>Non-treatment and Treatment Period</i>	23
3.4.2 <i>Pre- and Post-interview</i>	24
3.5 METHOD OF DATA ANALYSIS	24
CHAPTER 4: FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS.....	25
4.1 FINDING.....	25
4.1.1 <i>Tests</i>	25
4.1.1.1 Immediate test results	25
4.1.1.2 Delayed test results.	28
4.1.2 <i>Interviews</i>	30
4.1.2.1 Pre-interviews	30
4.1.2.1.1 Students' normal way of vocabulary learning.....	30
4.1.2.1.2 Students' perception about unrelated clustering.	31
4.1.2.1.3 Students' perception about thematic clustering.....	31
4.1.2.2 Post-interviews	32
4.1.2.2.1 Students' perception about unrelated clustering.	32
4.1.2.2.2 Students' perception about thematic clustering.....	33
4.1.2.2.3 Students' preference and self-evaluation.	34
4.1.2.2.4 Students' suggestion for classroom use.	34
4.1.3 <i>General findings</i>	35
4.2 DISCUSSION.....	36
4.2.1. <i>Studying vocabulary using thematic clustering facilitate students' vocabulary acquisition</i>	36
4.2.2. <i>Studying vocabulary using thematic clustering facilitate students' vocabulary recognition and production</i>	38
CHAPTER 5: CONCLUSION	40
5.1 THE HYPOTHESES REVISITED.....	40
5.2 IMPLICATIONS	40
5.2.1 <i>Theoretical implications</i>	40
5.2.2 <i>Implications for teaching English vocabulary and developing materials</i>	41
5.2.3 <i>Methodological implications</i>	41
5.3 LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY AND RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH	41
BIBLIOGRAPHY	43
APPENDICES	56

APPENDIX A56
APPENDIX B57
APPENDIX C59
APPENDIX D66
APPENDIX E67

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 4.1	26
------------------	----

LIST OF TABLES

Table 4.1	25
Table 4.2	27
Table 4.3	27
Table 4.4	28
Table 4.5	29
Table 4.6	29

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

EFL: English as a Foreign Language

ESL: English as a Second Language

L1: First language, native language

L2: Second language

H1: Hypotheses 1

H2: Hypotheses 2

NH1: Null Hypotheses 1

NH2: Null Hypotheses 2

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

This chapter presents the relevant context revolve the notion of thematic clustering as well as set out the reasons why there is a need to carry out research in this field. The purpose of the research is to compare the effect of thematic versus unrelated clustering on memory recognition and retention. Also, the significance of the present study will be pinpointed. Finally, an overview of the paper structure will be included.

1.1 Rationale of the study

Vocabulary, defined by Hoshino (2010) as the basis of language, has reached its traces of popularity in the field of English language, thus being recognized as an honor visitor in recent pedagogical research (Bogaards & Laufer, 2004; Coady & Huckin, 1997; Erten & Tekin, 2008; Read, 2000; Richards & Renandya, 2002). Since language is supposed to be meaningless without vocabulary (Sarioglu, 2018), it should be the one aspect that receives foremost attention in language teaching (Al Jabri, 2005) and should be pinpointed as a factor facilitating second language learning progress (Zargosh, Karbalaei, & Afraz, 2013). It is clearly stated by Willis (1990) that “without grammar very little can be conveyed, without vocabulary nothing can be conveyed” (pp. 111), and Nation (2006) also asserts that the amount of vocabulary needed per person can be up to 8,000 to 9,000 words, equivalent to 98% vocabulary coverage in order to understand a newspaper and a novel.

Of the many dimensions of research in this area witnesses a variety of ways to study vocabulary where thematic clustering (Gholami & Khezrlou, 2013; Markman & Hutchinson, 1984; Tinkham, 1997) is one approach beside the other type of word lists, namely taxonomic associate (Markman & Hutchinson, 1984), contextualization (Rahimi, 2014), semantic clustering (Finkbeiner & Nicol, 2003; Hashemi &

Gowdasiaei, 2005; Waring, 1997), code-switching and code-mixing (Ayemoni, 2006; Amuda, 1989; Atoye, 1994; Belly, 1976; Bokamba, 1989), to name a few.

Supporting the conclusion drawn by several researchers following the distinctiveness hypothesis (Tinkham, 1997, 2000), thematic clustering, according to Gholami and Khezrlou (2013), is the lexical set of vocabulary binding upon a specific schema formed on the basis of the arrangement of groups of words. Tinkham (1997) and Rahimi (2014) assert that as the psychological association of words grouping that are closely related to a common theme, or thematic concept, thematic clustering is believed to not only hinder the interference impact results from its rival concept, semantic clustering (Ishii, 2013; 2014), but also play a beneficial role in a better lexical retention (Tinkham, 1997).

Tracing back to the situation in Vietnam, empirical investigations reveal that Vietnamese learners have quite limited vocabulary knowledge, especially understanding the equivalent meaning as well as word forms (Dang, 2020; Nguyen, 2017; Tran, 2013; Vu & Nguyen, 2019). In addition, delve into the field in questions, thematic clustering received most of the empirical attention in a context where English is considered to be the first or second language, and the context of previous research about thematic clustering often carries out on bilingual or monolingual participants (Sarioglu & Yildirim, 2018; Zarei & Adami, 2013; Zarei & Arasteh, 2011). Therefore, regardless of the existence of empirical studies about thematic clustering, there is a lack of concentration in the learning environment where English has its background as a foreign language. Moreover, while previous studies considered thematic clustering only as a minor element beside other lexical categories such as semantic clustering, contextualization, code-mixing, etc. (Belly, 1976; Bokamba, 1989; Gholami & Khezrlou, 2013; Hippner Page, 2000; Smiley & Brown, 1979), with exception given in a few studies (Tinkham, 1997), thematic clustering, standing alone, can have either stronger or weaker impacts that need to be investigated further. The level of participants, additionally, also raises such a concern.

Because previous studies only investigated certain learners, including advanced learners or very young children (Hippner-Page, 2000; Markman & Hutchinson, 1984; Smiley & Brown, 1979; Tinkham, 1997) it is possible that a study about thematic clustering on a different level of learners, for example, elementary or pre-intermediate, comes up with different outcomes. Finally, since empirical studies came up with conclusions solely based on the results of immediate and delayed posttests, the results of those tests are quite fixed in numbers and do not reflect the nature of the phenomenon, i.e., prove that thematic clustering is effective or ineffective (Alshaikhi, 2011; Hippner-Page, 2000; Hoshino, 2010; Rahmati & Helmiyadi, 2021; Smiley & Brown, 1979).

It is clear that all the key reasons as abovementioned reflect the demand for researchers to further investigate the field of thematic clustering; therefore, the current study places thematic clustering as a major categorization and attempts to highlight it by putting thematic clustering next to unrelated clustering to witness the impact of thematic clustering on recognition and retention. Additionally, by focusing purposely on pre-intermediate level learners of English as a foreign language, the current paper gives insight into the impact of thematic clustering and also delves into the attitudes and behaviours of the students studying thematic clustering approach.

1.2 Statement of purpose

This study aims to investigate the effect of thematic clustering on studying vocabulary by utilizing a single-subject experimental design. In particular, the results of the experiment will be used to administrate the effect of thematic clustering on vocabulary learning. In addition, the post-interview will be employed to explore the attitudes and behaviors of participants who experienced thematic clustering.

1.3 Research hypotheses

The proposed hypotheses of the study are laid out as follow:

H1: Students believe that studying vocabulary using thematic clustering facilitate the process of vocabulary acquisition of students rather than using unrelated clustering.

H2: Studying vocabulary using thematic clustering can enhance students' vocabulary recognition and production.

Also, the null hypotheses are hereby set out:

NH1: Students believe that studying vocabulary using thematic clustering hinder the process of vocabulary acquisition of students rather than using unrelated clustering.

NH2: Studying vocabulary using thematic clustering cannot enhance students' vocabulary recognition and production.

1.4 Significance of the study

The study will be good use for several purposes. Firstly, this study benefits students who have not come up with a certain method of vocabulary learning or who want to explore different approaches of learning new words. Secondly, for course designers, textbook writers, or teachers, the results of this study can have a beneficial role for those who want to make adaptations, modifications, or even design coursebooks and textbooks using thematic or unrelated approach, as employed in this study, or a combination of both methods. Finally, this study can be useful for future research that investigates the same issue, i.e., thematic clustering, within the context of Vietnam or in the context of English as a foreign language.

1.5 Overview of the thesis chapters

This study is organized into five chapters. The first chapter sets out the introduction of thematic clustering and raises fundamental points pertaining to the nature of thematic clustering in a pedagogical context, i.e., within vocabulary study.

Chapter two provides relevant theoretical perspectives on thematic clustering and reflects empirical evidence about this field by reporting, summarizing, and analyzing past results. The next chapter deals with issues belonging to the methodology aspect of the result and accounts for the understanding of the research topic as well as the phenomenon. Chapter four displays the findings of the study and confirms the hypotheses set out earlier. Further discussion of revolving research is also included in this chapter, including a comparison of the current findings with previous conclusions. Finally, chapter five accounts for the final conclusion of the paper, with an informative summary, limitations, and recommendations for future researchers.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter focuses on both theoretical and empirical issues related to thematic clustering, which is divided into different sections. The first section regulates relevant theoretical perspectives including the definition, function of thematic clustering and its higher-level concept of schemata theory. This section also presents the overarching theory of the current study, which is distinctiveness hypothesis. Finally, the second section demonstrates and elaborates previous studies following the revelation of reflection leading to the ultimate purpose of this paper.

2.1 Relevant theories

The study was based on the ultimate theory set out by Tinkham (1997). Accordingly, Tinkham (1997) pointed out that the words belonging to different categories of semantic or thematic clusters fall under a common covering concept, i.e., frames (of schemata theory), and can be grouped together as a result of sorting out such syntactic characteristics. He also explained the arrangement, which is the application of schemata theory, whereby same lexical items jointed to gather into a set of same features play the role of distinction in memory. In addition, Hunt and Elliot (1980) suggest that the impact of long-term memory results in items sharing semantic and thematic clustering. Therefore, the concept of distinctiveness hypothesis acts as a manipulation of the distinctiveness level of the lexical items to increase memory retention (Tinkham, 1997). All the relevant concepts thereby will be discussed in detail in this section.

2.1.1 *Thematic clustering*

Several empirical studies have concentrated on studying the effect of semantic clustering (Tinkham, 1997; Waring, 1997). Until the study of Tinkham (1997) proposed an alternative method of word clustering called thematic clustering, the terms thematically associated clusters, thematically related clusters, or simply thematic clustering became popular (Allahverdizadeh, Shomoossi, Salahshoor &

Seifoori, 2014). Thematic clustering, according to Tinkham (1997), is a type of word combination originated from different parts of speech that is knit-tied with a common thematic concept and based upon the psychological associations between the same thematic concept of clustering. The nature behind the organization of such concepts is the arrangement of words from different syntactic categories that share the same set of circumstances linked together to become a single unit by co-describing a certain situation, the primary basis of which form such an arrangement based on the theory of semantic frames (Allahverdizadeh et al., 2014; Chepyshko & Truscott, 2009). Thus, Tinkham (1997), as cited in Hippner-Page (2000), believes that thematic clustering “taps into both cognitive and linguistic processes and result in better word learning environment” (pp. 10). The relatable relationship between the notion of thematic clustering and its application is discussed further in later sections.

The reflection and recognition of thematic clusters can be framed within a so-called “semantic frame”, which is the embodiment of people’s knowledge of a certain lexical pattern by understanding the background frames that are embedded within the concepts denoted by the words (Zarei & Arasteh, 2011). This idea was later explained further by Allahverdizadeh et al.,(2014) that although lexical items are among the distinctive syntactic and semantic categories, their participation traces back to participate within certain frame, or frames, or concepts reflecting partitioning of a speaker’s background knowledge, so-called “schemata”. The concept of “schemata” or “schemata theory”, therefore, will also be discussed in detail in a later section.

2.1.2 Schemata theory

The earliest definition for schemata theory came from the study of Bartlett (1932) as the way of actively organizing past actions or past experiences in order to operate a logical and brevity response. Schemata theory, as further defined by Filmore (1985), is the answer to the question of how human knowledge is reserved in the human brain. In fact, the study by Tracey and Morrow (2006) indicates the purpose of this theory is to explore humans’ methods of knowledge acquisition and

application. Ultimately, the three aspects that formulate the theory examined by Reason (1990) are those that fulfill the requirements of unconscious mental structures, the structure of previous knowledge, and the combination of active images that make up long-term memory. The study of Alshaikhi (2011) draws up an instance of schemata theory using the term “deposit”. When a person pops up the image of a bank, several terms linked with the lexical items will be brought up, as in the case that the word “bank” will be conjected upon the appearance of “bank”, and the similar situation happens for other terms, e.g., cheque, customer service, money, etc. (Alshaikhi, 2011).

While the concept of “semantic clusters” can be denoted by the area of “semantic fields”, the study of Filmore (1985) came up with a corresponding theory for “thematic clusters”, i.e. “semantic frames”, which lie under the superordinate theory of schemata (Tinkham, 1997). In fact, several studies have followed the path of this theory, two of which are Goetz, Anderson and Scharlett (1981) and Smith, Adams and Schorr (1978). The former came up with the idea that it is easier to learn a clause or sentence characterized with higher integration level and schema-related information than one with a schema-unrelated set of lexical items (Smith, Adams & Schorr, 1978). The latter also concluded in the same way, except for the adjustments of a whole sentence instead of a single phrase or clause (Goetz, Anderson & Scharlett, 1981). An explanation for the facilitating result is the lack of familiarity factors among unrelated-semantic information, and thus, the study also proves the application of schemata theory in a pedagogical context (Carrell, 1987; Smith, Adams & Schorr, 1978). The contribution function of schemata theory to the distinctiveness hypothesis will be discussed in later section.

2.1.3 Distinctiveness hypothesis

Another way to approach the concept of thematic clustering is through the explanation of distinctiveness hypotheses (Hunt & Elliot, 1980; Hunt & Elliot, 1982; Tinkham, 1997). Rooted back to the general belief that words are restored in memory

under the form of smaller features (Anisfeld & Knapp, 1968; Bower, 1967; Underwood, 1969), the features of which range from nonsemantic features such as orthographic and phonemic as visual and auditory representation, to semantic features as an abstract property of conceptual meaning (Hunt & Elliot, 1980). Not only are these features different in their nature, according to Hunt and Elliot (1980), they are also distinct in their application to memory restoration, in particular trace durability. While nonsemantic information is known as transient and cannot facilitate long-term memory, semantic information is widely known as a major support for memory retention (Hunt and Elliot, 1980).

Previous research has attempted to prove the effectiveness of semantic information through the conceptualization of encoding, namely stage levels (Atkinson & Shiffrin, 1968; ; Baddeley, 1966; Bruce & Murdock, 1968; Dale & Baddeley, 1969; Kintsch & Buschke, 1969; Nelson & Borden, 1973; Nelson & Brooks, 1973; Nelson, Brooks & Fosselman, 1972; Nelson, Brooks & Borden, 1974; Nelson, Reed & McEvoy, 1977; Nelson, Wheeler & Brooks, 1976; Waugh & Norman, 1965) and levels of processing (Brandsford & Franks, 1971; Craik & Lockhart, 1972; Craik & Tulving, 1975; Johnson & Jenkins, 1971; Johnson-Laird & Stevenson, 1970; Sachs, 1967; 1974; Schulman, 1974). the research support stage levels approach (Baddeley, 1966; Bruce & Mardock; 1968; Dale & Baddely, 1969; Walsh & Jenkins, 1973) is based on the theory that the trace durability encoded within memory is not the same in short-term memory and long-term memory, as those in short-term memory tend to be more transient and based on nonsemantic information, while those in the latter have a higher degree of duration and belong to semantic information (Hunt & Elliot, 1980). Considered as another alternative method, research following the levels of processing approach purportedly suggests that it is the qualitative nature of words features that defines the degree of retention by extracting stronger or weaker trace durability during encoding, as in the case of processing nonsemantic characteristics, which is equivalent to poorer retention and weaker trace durability, while semantic processing can demonstrate a better

performance and a greater level of trace durability (Craik & Lockhart, 1972). The data received in all studies either admit the apparent effect of semantic information on long-term memory and retention through lexical representation, or act as a clarification and strengthen the importance of such semantic information in the field, though the data following stage levels seem to be vague since they do not directly recognize the role of semantic information rather than just jump to conclusions by negating the effect of nonsemantic partners (Hunt & Elliot, 1980).

Based on previous research, in particular the levels of processing approach, the distinctiveness hypothesis is the main modification of this approach, which directly emphasizes the function of distinctive features in memory retention by measuring the trace durability, according to Eysenck, 1979; Hunt and Mitchell, 1978; Jacoby, 1975; Jacoby and Craik, 1979. Defined as the common lexical representation shared by other words, according to Hunt & Elliot (1980), distinctive features can be either semantic or nonsemantic features. Hunt and Elliot (1980) present a set of six experiments to test the hypothesis that the increase in retention results in an increase in distinctiveness. The results from these experiments showed that highlighting the distinctive features can lead to better recall, and such retention is rooted in the relevant degree of lexical representation shared by a set of words. Therefore, several conclusions can be drawn from the study of Hunt and Elliot (1980). Firstly, the distinctive features of a word can be various, ranging from a particular or abstract semantic or nonsemantic representation, either invisible or visible and physical. Secondly, by manipulating items sharing distinctive features, i.e., items sharing the same set of semantic frames under the concept of schemata theory, either semantic or thematic, the performance of subjects to recognize and recall such lexical representation can be improved by highlighting its distinctive features. The results of these experiments, therefore, are the formulation of the concepts of distinctiveness hypotheses. In fact, several later studies have applied the hypotheses of distinctiveness (Nelson, 1979; Stein, 1978). Distinctiveness hypotheses, therefore, became a framework to consider the retention quality of word features, which focus

on the qualitative aspects of memory trace and trace durability, i.e., whether the words features can retain in long or short duration, by pointing out the demonstration of such features regarding the utility and function of trace durability (Hunt and Elliot, 1980). Later, it is brought up in several studies investigating the field of semantic and also thematic vocabulary (Hippner Page, 2000; Mirijalili et al., 2012; Tinkham, 1997; etc.), with the belief that “as the distinctiveness (nonsimilarity) of the (same lexical items) information to be learnt increases, the ease of learning that information also increases” (Tinkham, 1997, p. 140). The distinctiveness hypothesis, therefore, also became the framework for the present study.

2.2 Previous studies

Delve into the past, several studies have been taken place to investigate the effect of thematic clustering on the study of vocabulary (Al Shaikhi, 2011; Allahverdizadeh, Shomoossi, Salahshoor & Seifoori, 2014; Hippner-Page, 2000; Hoshino, 2010; Zargosh, Karbalaei & Afraz, 2013; Khayef & Khoshnevis, 2012; Mirjalili, Jabbari & Rezai, 2012; Rahmati & Helmiyadi, 2021; Tinkham, 1997; Zarei & Arasteh, 2011; Zarei & Adami, 2013). While some researchers conclude thematic word lists to have a beneficial role on vocabulary receptive and production (Allahverdizadeh, Shomoossi, Salahshoor & Seifoori, 2014; Rahmati & Helmiyadi, 2021; Hippner-Page, 2000; Khayef & Khoshnevis, 2012; Mirjalili, Jabbari & Rezai, 2012; Tinkham, 1997; Zarei & Arasteh, 2011; Zarei & Adami, 2013; Zargosh, Karbalaei & Afraz, 2013;), the others postulate this type of organization to pose no effect or even hinder the learners’ ability to recall and retain new words (Al Shaikhi, 2011; Hoshino, 2010; Smiley and Brown, 1979).

Supported by the belief of Rahmati & Helmiyadi (2021), one of the urgent demands for learners is to understand new concepts, facilitated by having a deep understanding of new vocabulary, as the decrease in text understanding results in the increase in the difficulty of words (Mukoroli, 2011; cited by Rahmati & Helmiyadi, 2021). Rahmati and Helmiyadi (2021) also indicated that vocabulary learning

depends on the methods that learners acquire new words. So far, researchers have investigated thematic clustering by placing it beside other types of word lists (Hippner-Page, 2000; Zarei & Arasteh, 2011; Zargosh, Karbalaei & Afraz, 2013).

Follow the aforementioned conclusion, the study of Zarei and Arasteh (2011) combining thematic grouping with code-mixing and contextualization through a set of proficiency tests to use a set of tests to measure the effectiveness of each method regarding L2 vocabulary recognition and production. Zarei and Arasteh (2011) then came to the idea that thematic clustering shows the most distinguished outcome, while code mixing and contextualization showed no significant difference among the clusterings.

Broadening the range of participants to both monolingual and bilingual learners, Zargosh, Karbalaei, and Afraz (2013) focus only on examining the effect of thematic clustering on L1 and L2 students in terms of vocabulary acquisition. The study found that thematic clustering can have an effective impact on both L1 and L2 students but has a more significant effect on L2 students when they learn new words.

Similar to the research of Zargosh, Karbalaei, and Afraz (2013), the research by Zarei and Adami (2013) measures the effectiveness of the three methods on L2 learners' vocabulary recognition and retention, jumps to the conclusion that thematic clustering and notebook keeping are more effective than semantic mapping on recognition. Furthermore, researchers found out all three methods are effective on vocabulary production, but since thematic outperforms the other two, it is the most effective technique in both receptive and productive vocabulary knowledge, which is supported by Khayef and Khoshnevis's (2012) viewpoint as presented later in this chapter.

Another way to look into the effect of this type of clustering, invented by Tinkham (1997) and later followed by Allahverdizadeh, Shomoossi, Salahshoor and Seifoori (2014), is to categorize the set of clusters into related - unrelated semantic

clustering and associated - unassociated thematic clustering. Tinkham (1997) used a mixed factorial design to investigate whether the subjects found it more difficult to learn either related or unrelated semantic clusters, or whether it was easier for them to learn either associated or unassociated sets of thematic clusters. By using sets of artificial words followed and controlled strictly by rules and conditions, Tinkham (1997) counted the number of trials each subject needs to study vocabulary, therefore coming up with the result that semantic clustering impedes the learning process while thematic clustering, on the other hand, facilitates the overall progress that makes learners learn new words easier. He also pointed out that students learned thematically related sets much easier than the sets of unassociated clustering.

Followed by Tinkham (1997), the study of Allahverdizadeh, Shomoossi, Salahshoor and Seifoori (2014) examined the effect of thematic and semantic word lists on elementary learners with a bilingual background. The study supported Tinkham's (1997) conclusion by stating the strongest effect belongs to thematically associated sets, followed by semantically unrelated and thematically unassociated clustering, and the least effective method was semantically related clustering.

Another viewpoint that explores the thematic clustering effect regarding immediate vocabulary recall and retention on L2 learners comes from the study of Khayef and Khoshnevis (2012) and the one by Rahmati and Helmiyadi (2021). In particular, the study of Khayef and Khoshnevis (2012) investigated the effect of semantic and thematic clustering on EFL learners in terms of immediate memory and retention. Prioritizing an experimental design, the study figured out thematic clustering was superior in terms of immediate posttest and retention, while semantic clustering only performed better than the comparison group in immediate posttest but not on delayed posttest. Researchers, therefore, conclude that semantic clustering showed less impact on retention as compared to its partner, thematic grouping.

The study by Rahmati and Helmiyadi (2021) was, moreover, classroom action research which studied the effect of using thematic vocabulary cards in increasing

student English vocabulary in a primary school. The result in this study facilitated an implication for previous studies by indicating thematic clustering plays a significant role in enhancing students' ability to identify and remember new English vocabulary available in the given descriptive texts.

Normally, previous studies set up thematic clustering prioritizing an isolation concept, whereby testing receptiveness and retention reflect only the isolation of the word lists without the interference of contextualization (e.g., Tinkham, 1997). The study of Mirjalili, Jabbari and Rezai (2012), however, concentrated on studying the effect of semantic and thematic clustering using isolation and contextualization settings upon three levels of learners: elementary, pre-intermediate and intermediate learners. Findings in this study reflected thematic clustering having an apparent effect when recalling words in the setting of contextualization, while learners appeared to recall better upon learning unrelated sets of words when the words were being instructed to students in isolation.

Nonetheless, a few contrasting arguments state that thematic clustering does not prevail or hinder vocabulary learning, as in the studies of Al Shaikhi (2011), Hoshino (2010) and Smiley and Brown (1979). As an initiated in the area who focus on a potential factor that can control the cognitive process of acquiring new words, i.e., an age-related factor, Smiley and Brown (1979) look into the conceptual preference for thematic or taxonomic matching tasks from preschoolers to college students. Although they admitted that young and elderly individuals prefer thematic matching, middle school students and adults prefer a taxonomic system of organization. Smiley and Brown (1979) then explained that the changes in organization types are more than "preference shifts rather than a fundamentally new way of organizing new knowledge" (pp. 249). The study of Hoshino (2010), however, underrated thematic clustering under the other types of word categorization when comprising five types of word lists: synonyms, antonyms, categorical, thematic, and

arbitrary. He concluded that categorical lists are more effective than thematic and other types of word lists, which is in contrast to Tinkham's (1997) result.

Finally, inspired by Tinkham (1997), the study of Al Shaikhi (2011) investigated the most effective method of clustering vocabulary for Arabic-speaking advanced learners upon retention and acquisition. By applying Tinkham (1997), and later Allahverdizadeh, Shomoossi, Salahshoor and Seifoori (2014) word subdivisions, he separated semantic and thematic clustering into semantically related, semantically unrelated, and thematically related. Aims to define the most effective method of clustering vocabulary on Arabic-speaking advanced learners upon retention and acquisition; the research found no significant result on immediate tests within the three groups, but semantically related and unrelated groups outperformed thematic groups on delayed tests. The result is that, again, thematic clustering is considered the least effective method.

Although there are several studies looking into thematic grouping (Tinkham, 1997; Waring, 1997), this type of semantic analysis feature has received little consensus of its effectiveness. Further research is needed to define whether thematic clustering facilitates or prevents the process of vocabulary learning in terms of recognition and retention. Furthermore, the use of artificial or pseudo-words, as in the study of Tinkham (1997), makes the research per se impossible in a real classroom setting, and thus doubts its application, i.e., whether the same thing happens when using real words with less strictly followed rules and conditions. In addition, because previous studies have mostly concentrated on studying the effect of thematic clustering on L2 or L2 learners (Hippner-Page, 2000; Smiley & Brown, 1979), there is little empirical evidence showing that the effectiveness of thematic clustering will be the same in a classroom environment where English is studied as a foreign language. Therefore, the present study aims to investigate the effect of thematic grouping on foreign learners of English by measuring its effectiveness on vocabulary

recognition and production and exploring the learners' attitude toward and preference for these features of this semantic analysis.

CHAPTER 3: METHODOLOGY

This chapter of the study specifies the overall methodology as an attempt to determine the impact of thematic clustering on the study of vocabulary regarding memory recognition and retention. First, a general method is provided, along with the research designs and research instruments. Then, the study depicts the procedure to collect data, including information about participants. Finally, the means of data analysis are also laid out.

3.1 Research design

While empirical evidence prioritized the case of either experimental or quasi-experimental study (Allahverdizadeh, Shoomoossi, Salahshoor & Seifoori, 2014; Alshaikhi, 2011; Hippner Page, 2000; Hoshino, 2010; Khayef & Khoshnevis, 2012; Markman, 1984; Mirjalili, Jabbari & Rezai, 2012; Rahimi, 2014; Rahmati & Helmiyadi, 2021; Romero, 2009; Sarioglu & Yildirim, 2018; Smiley & Brown, 1979; Tinkham, 1997; Zarei & Arasteh, 2011; Zarei & Adami, 2013; Zargosh, 2013), this study took quite a deeper approach toward choosing a particular type of experimental design: single-subject design. Given the basis that single-subject design allowed researchers to explore the causal relationship between the intervention and outcome (Nock, Michel & Photos, 2007), the study aimed to test the effect of thematic clustering on the studying vocabulary regarding recognition and retention. The study also focused on the reasons lying behind the result of each individual, the nature of the study, thus, formulated the explanation for choosing such a single-subject design: to facilitate sources of information on the basis of single individuals (Creswell, 2012). Single subject design, according to Creswell (2012), involves studying individuals by observing them over a baseline period and administering an intervention to determine its corresponding impact on the outcome. In this case, the study expected to observe

the process of learning unrelated clustering vocabulary by the students, before conducting the thematic clustering intervention to witness if there were any corresponding impact on vocabulary recognition and retention. In addition, the unique aspect of single-subject design was that the single individual in the study becomes its own control in the experiment (Cooper, Heron & Heward, 1987; Neuman & McCormick, 1995), which was also facilitate the purpose of this research, i.e. to observe the behaviour and attitude of each student given treatment.

The independent variables were defined as the type of clustering: unrelated clustering or thematic clustering, while the dependent variable was determined by the students' results. Utilizing the advantageous of both qualitative and quantitative data, as the convergence and combination of both data sources could provide a comprehensive analysis of the research problem (Creswell & Creswell, 2018), the study combined both quantitative data from the tests scoring and qualitative data from interview recordings to test the distinctiveness hypothesis and the corresponding attitude and behaviour of participants.

More specifically, research comprised three main phases: non-treatment as a baseline, the intervention using treatment, and the interviews. Firstly, the pre-interview acted as a filter to reduce students with prior knowledge. which was also a part of non-treatment phase. Then, in the non-treatment period, the researcher set up a stable baseline of the current vocabulary studying approach to see how the students normally learn vocabulary, the baseline as such plays a role of minimize the possibility that there was an upward or downward trend in the students' behaviour pre-intervention (Poling & Grosset, 1986; as cited in Creswell, 2012). Next, the intervention phase was where all the observations and scoring of individuals took place repeatedly and frequently (Creswell, 2012), indicated the changing in the behaviour of students as they access the thematic clustering approach. Furthermore, as the researcher primarily focused on plotting the data of individuals rather than those from groups, there was the final post-treatment interview period where the

quantitative data recorded from tests in earlier sessions were explored further, as well as students' reasoning were collected.

3.2 Research instruments

This study involved a basic reversal pattern of a single-subject design, including a baseline period followed by an intervention treatment. In the baseline phase, students were presented with unrelated sets of lexical items, while in the later period, they were given access to thematic clustering of vocabulary to test the influence of the approach, as well as to make comparisons between the two. Additionally, the performance of participants was measured by a series of immediate and delayed tests, as in the studies of Hoshino (2010), Khayef and Khoshnevis (2012), Markman (1984), Mirjalili, Jabbari and Rezai (2012) and the one of Rahimi (2014), to test effective of the distinctiveness hypothesis. The study also carried out pre- and post-interviews to record the attitudes and behavior of participants regarding unrelated and thematic categorization, the data as such hoped to contribute for the lack of such interview data from previous evidence (Allahverdizadeh, Shoomoossi, Salahshoor, Seifoori, 2014; Alshaikhi, 2011; Hippner Page, 2000; Hoshino, 2010). Observations, similar to the procedure taken by Tinkham (1997), took place during the course of the study.

In this study, firstly, the vocabulary used in the study and the posttest in both baseline and intervention sections were adapted from the book "English Vocabulary In Use: Advanced Level" (McCarthy & O'Dell, 2017). Regarding the pre- and post-intervention interview, the interview questions were created by the researcher.

3.2.1 Vocabulary Item

The study adopted a set of 120 vocabulary items from the book "English Vocabulary In Use: Advanced Level" (McCarthy & O'Dell, 2017). The set of items were divided equally from 12 units, each unit belonged to the same advanced level and the vocabulary are within the range of B2 to C1 in the CEFR scale, so they were supposed to have no difference in levels. The adoption was made for two main

reasons. Firstly, the researcher chose to adopt items from an advanced course book because this level is higher than the current level of the participants, which was pre-intermediate. The intention of choosing a higher level was to reduce the risk of prior familiarity with the provided items, and therefore reduced the impact of potential extraneous variables. Secondly, in line with the study design, the lexical items were presented based on theme, which aligned with the purpose of the study and marked it as a priority choice over other course books.

The set of items was chosen from 12 different themes (see Appendix B), the first 6 of which were arranged randomly to create 6 sets of unrelated clustering vocabulary, each set containing 10 items. The last 6 themes had their order retained as thematic clustering items. Because all the vocabulary was used in the learning phase, either unrelated (non-treatment) or related (treatment), Vietnamese definitions were provided for all items, with priority given to presenting the closest piece of meaning that later on conducted in the tests. The facilitating of L1 equivalence was based on the fact that the more learners are familiar with the L1 meaning, the stronger the association formed between the English and the L1 definitions, i.e the relationship between the stimulus (L1) and the response (English words) in a pair-association learning, the association as which could enhance learning efficiency (Morikawa, 1955; Tagashira, 2010).

3.2.2 Tests

3.2.2.1 Immediate Tests

There was a total of 12 immediate posttests, all of which were designed using the materials and exercises in the same textbook (see Appendix C). The posttests were divided into 2 parts: the first half is created for the non-treatment period, and the latter belongs to the intervention phase. Compared to the learning phase, the order of items in the tests was randomly reversed to ensure they are in different orders than the vocabulary items presented earlier. Similar to the vocabulary sets, the first 6 posttests had all items shuffled to create questions with unrelated clustering. The last

6 posttests were in the same manner as the thematic clustering items, with the order of items in each posttest shuffled. Each test, regardless of the item arrangement, contained 10 gap-filling questions.

3.2.2.2 Delayed Tests

Overall, the delayed post-tests contained 120 questions. They made use of the materials in the same course book, together with the definitions from the Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary. The tests were also divided into two parts: one for unrelated items, and the other for thematic vocabulary. Each test contained 6 sections, with 60 vocabulary items in sets of 10, and in the form of gap-filling answers. The items were divided into sections to minimize students' confusion upon completing a test with a large number of questions.

3.2.3 Interviews

This study involved two separate sets of interviews. The pre-interview design aimed to explore the students' current method of learning vocabulary while the post-interview instrument delved into the attitude and behaviour of students before and after experiencing thematic clustering. The results of the interviews, together with the data from the tests, hoped to promote the impacts of thematic clustering as well as to prove the outcome of the distinctiveness hypothesis. Both interviews were conducted in Vietnamese, since it was supposed that the learners might face some difficulty while producing answers. The data were translated to English later by the researcher.

3.2.3.1 Pre-interviews

The researcher created a total of 3 interview questions under the form of open-ended questions to give participants freedom of giving answers (see Appendix D). Question number 1 concentrated on exploring students' current method of learning vocabulary, which also helped to reduce participants with prior background knowledge. The rest two questions figured out students' perception on learning vocabulary based on unrelated word lists and thematic word lists. The two types of

clustering, thus, were explained to students in a simple way, with illustrated examples before asking for students' opinions.

3.2.3.2 Post-interviews

The researcher designed a total of 5 interview questions also structured in an open-ended format that encourages students to provide answers and further explanation (see Appendix E). The first and second questions focused on asking participants about their feelings and attitudes towards their experience in the two phases, in order to compare their reactions between the method used during the baseline and the intervention. The next question confirmed students' perceptions about each method, i.e their preferences. Question number four asked students to evaluate and compare the effectiveness of each type of clustering they experienced earlier, and the final question shedded light on participants' suggestions for pedagogical implications, i.e the type of clustering they would suggest for classroom implementation.

3.2.4 Observations

The observations were conducted throughout the course of the study. In the pre- and post-interviews, the researcher observed the participants' answers and acts as a moderator to clarify or expand information collected. During the intervention, the researcher made necessary attempt to ensure the objective of the experiments, i.e to make sure the students do not capture or note down the vocabulary by any means. In addition, the researcher kept track of the time taking for while presenting the vocabulary, i.e to notice the students and stop screen sharing after 4 minutes. The researcher also observed the time students taking the tests.

3.3 Participants

The participants attending the experiments were six university students from different universities in Ho Chi Minh City, with their age ranging from 18 to 22. The participants were from three different classes with the same level in an english center in Ho Chi Minh City, so they were supposed to have the same level of

approximately pre-intermediate level. The study gave priority to this level based on the fact that empirical studies primarily focused on either participant with higher background, i.e advanced level (Tinkham, 1997; Hippner Page, 2000; Markman, 1984; etc.) or beginner level, i.e children from 3 to 5 years old (Smiley & Brown, 1979) with little attention paid on participants from elementary or pre-intermediate level. The participants were chosen based on purposeful sampling, with criteria given to their sameness of English level (different class but same level) and they volunteered to engage in the experiment. Purposeful sampling method was chosen because the students need to have the same English level in order to take part in the experiments. All the six participants took part in all the three parts of the experiment individually, i.e the baseline, intervention and the interview.

3.4 Research procedure

The study took place over a 7-week course, with 4 weeks of either non-intervention or intervention treatment, 2 weeks for delayed tests, and a final week for post-treatment interviews. The delayed tests were carried out one week after the last section of each phase, the time as such had been proved by several empirical research (Hippner Page; Hashemi & Gowdasiaei, 2005). Both the treatments and interviews were conducted individually and virtually using the Google Meet platform. In particular, the research procedure was separated into three phases. The first phase took place from week 1 to 3, where the first two weeks were spent on 6 sessions of non-treatment and immediate posttests, and the first delayed posttest occurred in week 3. The intervention phase happened from week 4 to 6, with weeks 4 and 5 dedicated to treatments and posttests, and the second delayed posttest carried out in week 6. Finally, in week 7, the post-treatment interviews were conducted.

Before the intervention, the participants were informed of their engagement one week in advance and a fixed schedule is arranged for their participation. As the researcher was also their teacher in class, they were given prior notice that their result in class was independent of the result of the study, and participation in the study

would not give them any privileges over other classmates (see Appendix A). Additionally, the students received a brief explanation about the project and the way it was carried out.

3.4.1 Non-treatment and Treatment Period

During the four-week intervention course, each participant attended 12 study sections and immediate post-tests carried out personally with the researcher. The first six sections were the non-intervention period, where students were given unrelated items and corresponding immediate post-tests. The last six sections belonged to the treatment period, with items categorized thematically and post-tests to investigate their effectiveness.

In either the baseline or treatment period, each student took part in three sections per week, each lasting approximately 20 minutes. In each section, the student learnt 10 vocabulary items in either thematic or unrelated categorization, which are presented in PowerPoint slides shared by the researcher. They had exactly four minutes, the duration of which had been proven by the study of Mirjalili, Jabbari & Rezai, 2012, to study the vocabulary. They were not allowed to capture or take note of the vocabulary items by any means in order to keep the study results objective. After four minutes, an immediate post-test was sent under a Google Form link. Although there was no time limit in the immediate post-test, the researcher, as a role of an invigilator, still tracked the time from the point the test was sent until it was submitted by the students.

The delayed post-tests were carried out one week after the last section of each part occurred, which was one week after section 06 and section 12. Similarly, there was no time allotted, but the researcher still recorded the time.

3.4.2 Pre- and Post-interview

Both interviews were carried out in Vietnamese. During the two interviews, the researchers acted as the role of a moderator to explain, ask follow-up questions, and clarify the information received.

The pre-interview occurred before the non-treatment period, which was part of the baseline phase. Each participant approached individually and directly without prior notice, and the entire interview lasted for about 15 minutes. The questions used were open-ended questions and the data collected was recorded.

The post-treatment interviews took place one week after the second phase, which follows the treatment phase. The participants were interviewed individually, and the entire interview lasted approximately 30 minutes. At the beginning of the interview, the students were informed that there are no right or wrong answers. During the process, the interviewer used open-ended questions to communicate with the participants. Questions for clarification were also used to ensure the quality of the collected data. Attempts were made to encourage students to give answers in detail, with explanations or examples as follow-ups. The students' answers were recorded with prior consent.

3.5 Method of data analysis

A one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) in SPSS version 22 was used to administer the results of immediate and delayed tests. Additionally, the data from the interview was transcribed and analyzed using Zoltan's (2006) four steps of data analysis. First, the data from the recordings was transcribed. Then, preparation was made for the pre-coding and coding phases. After pre-coding and coding, data from other forms of data displays were gathered to form the complete data bank. Finally, the data was interpreted, and the final report was written.

CHAPTER 4: FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

In this chapter, the findings and the discussion of the data will be discussed in detail. The first part of this chapter provides the result of the study, including the data from the tests and interview. The second section continues to further discuss about the remarkable outcome in comparison with other empirical evidence, and also explain the results.

4.1 Finding

4.1.1 Tests

Prior to the data analysis, the reliability of the instruments was calculated through Cronbach's alpha to check if they met the requirement of internal consistency. The reliability co-efficient was 0.847 for 24 items, which indicates acceptable internal consistency ($\alpha > 0.8$) (Peterson, 1994).

4.1.1.1 Immediate test results

Each participant was tested on two types of clustering: unrelated clustering and thematic clustering. The descriptive statistics in Table 4.1 show that students achieve higher scores in terms of thematic clustering ($M=5.42$), than unrelated clustering ($M=4.08$). This outcome also reflects on the minimum and maximum scores of each type of clustering, where thematic clustering possesses a minimum score of 3 and a maximum score of 8, which is higher in comparison to the data on unrelated clustering. Also, the standard deviation for both groups was nearly the same, at $SD = 1.519$ and $SD = 1.763$, which indicates quite similar variation. Finally, the data was not skewed indicates normal distribution in both groups (0.318 and 0.014 , respectively), which can also be proved in figure 4.1.

Table 4.1

Descriptive Statistics of Immediate Tests

	N Statistic	Minimum Statistic	Maximum Statistic	Mean Statistic	Std. Deviation Statistic	Skewness	
						Statistic	Std. Error
Unrelated clustering	36	2	7	4.08	1.519	.318	.393
Thematic clustering	36	3	8	5.42	1.763	.014	.393

Figure 4.1

Boxplot of immediate tests

As above mentioned, since the data was normally distributed, a One-Way Repeated ANOVA was run to determine whether or not there was a statistical significance on vocabulary recognition between the two types of clustering: unrelated clustering and thematic clustering. The study considered the following null hypothesis and alternative hypothesis:

Null Hypothesis: There was no statistically significant difference between unrelated clustering and thematic clustering regarding vocabulary recognition.

Alternative Hypothesis: There was a statistically significant difference between unrelated clustering and thematic clustering regarding vocabulary recognition.

Because the assumption from Mauchly's Test of Sphericity has been violated, the degrees of freedom were corrected using the result of Greenhouse-Geisser, at .000. The result showed that there was a statistically significant difference between the two groups ($F(1,35) = 15.56, p = .000$). Also, the Wilks' Lambda statistic of .692 (with $p < 0.05$) suggested that there was a change in scores between two groups. Finally, Partial Eta Squared of .308 suggested the result possessed a very large effect size according to the guideline proposed by Cohen (1988). Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative hypothesis, which stated the two methods were different from each other, was retained.

Table 4.2

Multivariate Tests

Effect		Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Immediate	Pillai's Trace	.308	15.556	1.000	35.000	.000	.308
	Wilks' Lambda	.692	15.556	1.000	35.000	.000	.308
	Hotelling's Trace	.444	15.556	1.000	35.000	.000	.308
	Roy's Largest Root	.444	15.556	1.000	35.000	.000	.308

Table 4.3

Tests of Within-Subjects Effects

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared

Immediate	Sphericity		1				
	Assumed	32.000		32.000	15.556	.000	.308
	Greenhouse-Geisser	32.000	1.000	32.000	15.556	.000	.308
	Huynh-Feldt	32.000	1.000	32.000	15.556	.000	.308
	Lower-bound	32.000	1.000	32.000	15.556	.000	.308
Error (Immediate)	Sphericity						
	Assumed	72.000	35	2.057			
	Greenhouse-Geisser	72.000	35.000	2.057			
	Huynh-Feldt	72.000	35.000	2.057			
	Lower-bound	72.000	35.000	2.057			

4.1.1.2 Delayed test results.

The results in delayed tests (Table 4.4) also demonstrated that students achieve higher scores on thematic clustering ($M = 6.08$, $SD = 1.948$) than on unrelated clustering ($M = 4.64$, $SD = 1.355$). The maximum score students achieved on thematic clustering was also better than on unrelated one, at 10 and 8, respectively. The data also meet the requirement of normal distribution, at 0.311 for unrelated clustering and 0.540 for thematic clustering.

Table 4.4

Descriptive Statistics of Delayed Tests

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std.	Skewness	
						Statistic	Std. Error
Unrelated clustering	36	2	8	4.64	1.355	.311	.393
Thematic clustering	36	3	10	6.08	1.948	.540	.393

A One-Way Repeated measures ANOVA is conducted to compare the production effect based on the scores obtained for the two types of clustering. The study also set out null hypothesis and alternative hypothesis as follow:

Null Hypothesis: There is no statistically significant difference between unrelated clustering and thematic clustering regarding vocabulary production.

Alternative Hypothesis: There is a statistically significant difference between unrelated clustering and thematic clustering regarding vocabulary production.

Though normally distributed, there was a violation regarding sphericity, so the result was considered using Greenhouse-Geisser degrees of freedom correction. The results illustrated that there was a statistically significant difference between unrelated clustering and thematic clustering ($F(1,35) = 14.53, p = 0.001$, Wilks' Lambda = .707 with a $p < 0.05$). The result also suggested a very large effect size Partial Eta Squared of .293 (see guidelines from Cohen, 1988). Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected while the alternative hypothesis was retained.

Table 4.5

Multivariate Tests

Effect		Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Delayed	Pillai's Trace	.293	14.533	1.000	35.000	.001	.293
	Wilks' Lambda	.707	14.533	1.000	35.000	.001	.293
	Hotelling's Trace	.415	14.533	1.000	35.000	.001	.293
	Roy's Largest Root	.415	14.533	1.000	35.000	.001	.293

Table 4.6

Tests of Within-Subjects Effects

Source		Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Delayed	Sphericity Assumed	37.556	1	37.556	14.533	.001	.293

	Greenhouse-Geisser	37.556	1.000	37.556	14.533	.001	.293
	Huynh-Feldt	37.556	1.000	37.556	14.533	.001	.293
	Lower-bound	37.556	1.000	37.556	14.533	.001	.293
<hr/>							
Error							
(Delayed)	Sphericity Assumed	90.444	35	2.584			
	Greenhouse-Geisser	90.444	35.000	2.584			
	Huynh-Feldt	90.444	35.000	2.584			
	Lower-bound	90.444	35.000	2.584			

4.1.2 Interviews

4.1.2.1 Pre-interviews

4.1.2.1.1 Students' normal way of vocabulary learning.

Students, upon being asked for their usual method of vocabulary learning, came up with two main methods to learn new words: unintentionally or intentionally. For those using unintentional learning, they tended to learn new words randomly based on frequently used words (A3), interests (A4 and A5), or contents on social media (A6). To clarify her point about learning by interests, student A4 explained, “*if we learn vocabulary based on topic, it will be too much to learn it all, so I just learn the one I like.*”

On the other hand, for those who prioritize learning intentionally, they rather relied on some kind of reading comprehension context and were only limited to the words that appeared within context (A1, A2, A5). However, the order of vocabulary learned either followed the reading order, such as listing out all items appeared in a single paragraph, or listing from top to bottom (A1, A2), or, as in one case of a student admitted she purposefully listed out the words based on a certain arrangement, for example, word forms or topic. She said, “*I learn the words through reading passages; for example, after reading, I will list out the words based on the topic to learn*” (A5). Nonetheless, some students admitted to having more than one method of learning. Student A3, beside learning randomly, admitted, “*I only learn the vocabulary in the reading passages or in a certain topic when I study at school.*”

4.1.2.1.2 Students' perception about unrelated clustering.

In terms of participants' comments on learning vocabulary by unrelated clustering, 4 out of 6 participants defined studying by unrelated clustering as difficult to learn and hard to remember (A1, A2, A3, A5). They mentioned various reasons, ranging from the irrelevance and separation between the meaning of the vocabulary to the wasting of time trying to remember the list of items. Only 1 student claimed that she felt normal learning this way, though she insisted that she would not remember it after a long time because she could only remember the chain of letters without imagining the words.

(A6) *"I think it is quite normal; I mean, I still can learn them, though maybe I cannot remember them for long because I cannot imagine the items and just attempt to remember the way the letters formed the words."*

In contrast, only 1 student had very positive preference towards learning in unrelated clustering with the explanation that it helps her to *"maximize the words learnt, the topic, as well as knowledge"* (A4). She also adds that she can learn the words if she is interested, and that her method of learning is solely independent of the types of clustering.

(A4) *"I think that even if the vocabulary is arranged randomly, I can still remember it, because for me, learning words is simply that if I want to remember them, I will remember them, which means I will not be affected by the words' lexical arrangements or other factors."*

4.1.2.1.3 Students' perception about thematic clustering.

Regarding vocabulary learning through thematic clustering, all the participants claimed that thematic clustering helped them learn and remember the vocabulary faster and longer. Generally, they came up with the explanation that the thematic clustering itself created some kind of common theme or contexts that linked the items together (A1, A5). Student A6 had quite a similar viewpoint when she said

that she could create an “*imaginary picture*” in her mind by forming and linking the image of each item. Nonetheless, in spite of sharing the same idea that thematic clustering supported learning vocabulary, student A6 believed that thematic clustering could only facilitate short-term memory but not long-term memory. However, she agreed “*it is a good way for me to broaden my vocabulary vertically (a common theme or topic) instead of horizontally (a different theme or topic).*”

4.1.2.2 Post-interviews

4.1.2.2.1 Students’ perception about unrelated clustering.

In light of answering the first interview question, 5 out of 6 students expressed that learning unrelated vocabulary was not effective for them, except in the case of student A4. They either claim it is impossible to learn all 10 words at once (A1, A2, A5), or it is only possible to store the words in short-term memory, which means they soon forget them after a short while (A3, A6).

(A5) “*I can only remember 1 or 2 words per section.*”

(A6) “*I can only remember some simple words this way, and I will drop out most of the others when they are so abstract.*”

They explained that the words are not easy to retain in their memory as they constantly get the incorrect match between the piece of vocabulary and its meaning, or sometimes unintentionally combine parts of different words (A1, A5). When asked why they came up with such feelings, some students expressed that it was likely because their brains had to constantly switch between disorderly imagination caused by the different pieces of lexical meaning of the words (A1).

(A5) “*Learning vocabulary in this way is not effective for me, I feel that after learning, the amount of vocabulary left in my head is not much. Words seem harder to remember and more chaotic because our brain has to constantly switch between discrete associations, and when we remember the next word, we will forget most of the earlier words.*”

The only case of student A4 defines this method as “*easy to learn*” and “*can be learnt in a short time*”. Upon asking for an explanation, she shared that it was the distinction of the words that, when placed next to each other, somehow highlighted each other, and the more different the words were, the faster she learnt.

(A4) “*I think this method is quite easy to learn, and I learn very quickly in a short time. I think the factor that makes me learn faster is that the more unrelated the words are, the more they are put together, the more they highlight each other, and the more different they are, the faster I will remember.*”

Finally, 5 out of 6 students expressed that the unrelated clustering method was harder to learn than their usual method of learning, except for student A4 with the opposite viewpoint.

4.1.2.2 Students’ perception about thematic clustering.

Concerning students’ attitudes toward thematic clustering, 5 out of 6 students agreed that this method facilitated their learning speed, i.e., they learnt faster, except for student A4. The reason they shared seemed similar to their answer in the pre-interview, i.e., they could imagine the picture of the items, or they could form a link among the set of items. In addition, 2 out of 6 students believed this method would help them increase the number of items remembered per time (A5) or facilitate the learning of terminology (A1).

(A1) “*I can even remember specialized words that are very difficult that if they are randomly arranged, I will not be able to remember them.*”

However, when asked about memory retention, all the participants seemed to have a neutral opinion, stating that it depended on different other factors such as the frequently used words (A2), the familiarity with the lexical equivalent meaning (A3), and the tendency to form the “*image*” of the words (A6).

(A6) *“For example, if you only have one word “red” you can only remember that word, but when you have a “house” and then you have a “picture” and it's red, you will pop up in your mind a picture of a house and the sky, with a red picture hanging on the wall.”*

Lastly, those who hold a positive view tended to evaluate thematic clustering as easier to learn compared to their usual learning method (5 out of 6 students), and vice versa (A4).

4.1.2.2.3 Students' preference and self-evaluation.

Aiming to investigate students' preferences and self-evaluation, questions three and four of the interview revealed that most of the participants shifted their preference toward thematic clustering and ranked this type of clustering as having higher effectiveness. Almost all students preferred thematic clustering because of the lexical connection among the vocabulary items (A2), the extent to which it helps one maximize the number of items learned per time (A1), and the extent to which it supports vocabulary retention (A1, A5). Simultaneously, the majority of participants assessed thematic clustering to be more effective, except in the case of A4. To strengthen their opinion, some students added that they only learnt unrelated words as a way to protest when having a school test or examination (A5, A6), while student A4 thought it cost her less time to learn the other way.

(A6) *“I only learn dozens of words at a time to protest when I go to school with a test. It is fine, though usually after studying, I will not remember them all.”*

4.1.2.2.4 Students' suggestion for classroom use.

Undertaking the question of whether or not to suggest either thematic clustering, unrelated clustering, or both types of clustering, participants followed quite an overlapping idea of choosing either thematic clustering or both thematic clustering and unrelated clustering. Half of the participants suggested thematic clustering to be publicly chosen (A1, A3, and A6). The favorable could be explained

by a diverse perspective, for example, “*build up the vocabulary systematically over a long period of time*” (A1) or “*apply in other skills, especially writing*” (A5). Despite their choices, these participants hold quite different opinions regarding their decision not to recommend unrelated clustering. They either stated that unrelated clustering should be applied to other course purposes, such as intensive courses (A1), or believed that unrelated clustering hindered vocabulary learning by making the items difficult to remember (A3) and should only be considered for fast learners (A6).

The rest of the students played neutral roles when choosing both types of clustering (A2, A4, and A5). Generally, they all agreed that it depended on each individual, i.e., each type of clustering would either facilitate or hinder the students. Additionally, they believed that it depended on the purpose of studying (A4, A5) and the time that an individual could devote to learning vocabulary (A4).

4.1.3 General findings

To sum up, the study came up with certain results in light of supporting the distinctiveness hypothesis. Firstly, the study revealed that students learning vocabulary who apply thematic clustering had better performance than those applying unrelated clustering. The increasing scores achieved by students for their immediate and delayed tests suggested that there was a positive development in students’ performance regarding thematic clustering rather than unrelated clustering. In addition, the results of the interviews indicated that the majority of participants expressed positive attitudes toward thematic clustering through pointing out their preferred types of clustering and self-evaluation. Furthermore, there was a tendency for students to suggest thematic clustering for use by schools, apart from some who recommended both types of clustering. Therefore, the hypothesis H1, saying that students believed studying vocabulary using thematic clustering facilitated the process of vocabulary acquisition rather than using unrelated clustering, was retained, and the null hypothesis NH1 was rejected.

Another conclusion that can be drawn from the study was that studying vocabulary using thematic clustering could enhance students' vocabulary recognition and production. However, the impact was much stronger in terms of vocabulary recognition than in the aspect of production. Evidence for this piece of conclusion could be found in the statistical descriptions and the results of the tests, including the immediate and delayed tests. In particular, the results from the immediate tests showed studying vocabulary using thematic clustering had a stronger effect than studying vocabulary using unrelated clustering, which indicated thematic clustering could enhance students' vocabulary recognition. Additionally, the results from the delayed tests demonstrated studying vocabulary using thematic clustering also had a significant effect compared to using unrelated clustering, which concluded thematic clustering could enhance students' vocabulary production. From the conclusion, the hypothesis H2, which stated that studying vocabulary using thematic clustering could enhance students' vocabulary recognition and production, was retained, the null hypothesis NH2, therefore, was rejected.

4.2 Discussion

4.2.1. Studying vocabulary using thematic clustering facilitate students' vocabulary acquisition

Firstly, the study reveals that studying vocabulary using thematic clustering facilitates students' vocabulary acquisition. This idea is similar to Allaverdizadeh et al.'s (2014) findings that participants recall more words from thematic sets than other types of word categorization. The researcher, however, realizes the effect is more noticeable for participants at elementary levels compared to those who are at intermediate levels. Therefore, he suggests the proficiency levels of participants may be incompatible with the impact of thematic features. This idea, later on, confirmed by the study of Al-Jabri (2005) who suggests that an increase in levels of proficiency leads to a decrease in the need for distinguishing words categorization. In other words, the lower the level of the students, the stronger an effect this type of clustering

can have on them, which can be a possible undertaking interpretation for the current finding.

Besides, the distinctiveness hypothesis and schema theory are proved to be supportive in the present results. The results also correspond with the findings of Mirjalili, Jabbari and Rezai (2012) that thematic clustering facilitates students' learning processes especially when combined with contextual-based learning, which is also a case that sheds light on the distinctiveness hypothesis and schema theory. One underlying reason can be found for the outcome of Hoshino's (2010) findings, which also play a role as facilitators for the distinctiveness hypothesis and schema theory. He explains that in cases where two words share just smaller features, like thematic clustering, rather than sharing bigger and overlapping features (as in the case of synonyms), the words can have certain supplementary functions, i.e., make it easier to remember.

Another factor that demands consideration is the position of the English language in the undertaking environment. Since the current finding also aligns with Zargosh, Karbalaei and Afraz's (2013) assertion, the enhancement impact of thematic clustering on vocabulary acquisition can be found not only in monolinguals and bilinguals, but also in an environment where English is a foreign language. In other words, the influence of thematic clustering represents an independent factor, regardless of the environment it settled in.

However, the study is incompatible with Hippner-Page's (2000) and Smiley and Brown's (1979) statements that thematic clustering has a neutral effect on students compared to other techniques. Possible reasoning provided by Hippner-Page's (2000) research asserts that the influence of clustering can be strengthened simultaneously with the increasing levels of familiarity among students. Furthermore, the study of Smiley and Brown (1979) adds that the equality in influence may be rooted in the change in preference rather than backed by any undertaking assumptions. Lastly, the current outcome is in contrast with the results from the study by Zarei and Adami

(2013), which indicate thematic clustering has no influence on vocabulary presentation. However, such a result is more predictable, as advocated by the interference hypothesis, which remains an up-to-date controversial counterpart of the distinctiveness hypothesis.

4.2.2. Studying vocabulary using thematic clustering facilitate students'

vocabulary recognition and production

Secondly, the study shows that studying vocabulary using thematic clustering has a significant effect on students rather than using unrelated clustering in terms of vocabulary recognition and production. Generally, this idea confirms the result of Tinkham's (1997) assertion that defines thematic clustering's contribution as a facilitator of learning through vocabulary recognition and recall, which simultaneously confirms the distinctiveness hypothesis and schema theory. This belief, however, does not correspond with Al Shaikhi's (2011) and Sarioglu and Yildirim's (2018) negation of the beneficial influence of thematic clustering on words receptive and productive. Instead, it is emphasized that the teachers need to concentrate on the amount of words taught in class and the method to teach them, rather than the clustering resolution (Sarioglu & Yildirim, 2018).

However, it is worth mentioning that the enhancement of vocabulary recognition and retention is not always a case of symmetrical correlation. A case investigated by Khayef and Khoshnevis (2012) also in parallel with the current findings when indicate that the role of thematic clustering is more remarkable for recalling words than words production. Therefore, the two aspects should be noticed as separate approaches, as in the case of Rahimi's (2014) and Zarei and Arasteh's (2011) findings. While the findings are in line with the current study in relation to vocabulary retention, i.e., they prove that thematic clustering can support vocabulary production, they are also contrary to the current findings considering vocabulary receptive, i.e., they show thematic clustering is not advantageous for vocabulary recognition. Khayef and Khoshnevis (2012), thus, suggest teachers need to spend

time training students in advance to use thematic clustering in a way that is most beneficial.

CHAPTER 5: CONCLUSION

The concluding section of this paper will begin by reiterating the established hypotheses and highlighting the key discoveries of the study. It will then delve into the practical implications of the paper in terms of theoretical, methodological, and educational aspects. Finally, the study will identify important insights for future research which come in lines of its limitations.

5.1 The hypotheses revisited

The research supports the hypotheses by pointing out that thematic clustering contributes to the study of vocabulary recognition and retention. Additionally, thematic clustering also proves the hypothesis of facilitating vocabulary acquisition in non-English speaking learners by confirming the students' preferences and positive attitudes toward this type of clustering.

5.2 Implications

The current paper has important implications for various theories, principles, and pedagogical aspects that have been mentioned. The results of the study have provided valuable insights that can inform and shape the understanding of theories and principles in the context of education. By reaching out to such implications, a broader understanding of the study's findings and the corresponding value of educational practices can be obtained. On the whole, the implementations of this paper can serve as a valuable resource for educators, researchers, and textbook designers who seek to incorporate these findings into their related work fields.

5.2.1 Theoretical implications

In brief, the distinctiveness hypothesis is one of the most widely studied models of clustering and has been applied to many different domains, including classification, document retrieval, and image segmentation (Gopalakrishnan, Pang & Kuo, 2009). By and large, it states that items in a cluster should be more similar to each other than they are to items outside of the cluster. Considering the study's

outcomes, the present paper suggests the distinctiveness hypothesis can hold true when applied to investigate the effectiveness of thematic clustering in comparison to other word categorization on the ground that participants can recall more distinctive items than non-distinctive ones.

5.2.2 Implications for teaching English vocabulary and developing materials

The results of this study may be helpful for material developers and textbook designers, particularly those interested in dealing with lexical categorization and vocabulary development. For this reason, adjustments can be made when arranging vocabulary items following the theme grouping instead of the alternative alphabetical or level grouping. Remarkably, the study thus recommends teachers integrate this method of clustering into teaching English vocabulary, essentially when increasing the number of words needed per person, leading to enhanced comprehension, is one of the students' objectives. However, further consideration shall be taken prior to jumping to the conclusion of taking thematic clustering either as an outstanding method or together with other types of word categorization.

5.2.3 Methodological implications

The final implication of this study accounts for research methodology. On top of the results, the study recommends approaching the participants, who are students at the center of the learning process, using experiment research, particularly the single-subject study, thereby delving into not only the statistical data but also the students' voices and experiences on the whole.

5.3 Limitations of the study and recommendations for future research

Although the study's generalization is maintained statistically and theoretically by using triangulation, the limitation of this study is the number of research participants. The nature of a single-subject study makes the sample size of this study quite small. Additionally, the levels of proficiency in this study cover a small scale of pre-intermediate levels. Furthermore, the study narrows down to concentrating on two types of clustering, which is quite limited compared to the big

picture of word categorization as a whole. Therefore, the study results might not be the same when applying a larger sample size with different proficiency levels or when taking other types of clustering into account.

Finally, as a final consideration for future research, it may be beneficial to explore the effects of thematic clustering in combination with other forms of word categorization on students with varying levels of proficiency in the foreign language. This approach can potentially yield more practical and applicable outcomes in the context of foreign language instruction. By further investigating this topic, researchers can gain a deeper understanding of how these techniques can be effectively utilized in language learning and teaching, particularly for students at different proficiency levels.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Al-Jabri, S.S. (2005). *The effects of semantic and thematic clustering on learning English vocabulary by Saudi students*. [PhD dissertation, Indiana University of Pennsylvania]. University of Pennsylvania.

Allahverdizadeh, M., Shomoossi, N., Salahshoor, F., & Seifoori, Z. (2014). Vocabulary acquisition and lexical training by semantic and thematic sets : A case of Persian learners of English. *Journal of Applied Linguistics and Language Research*, 1(1), 45-61.

Amuda A. A. (1989). Attitudes to code-switching: The case of Yoruba and English. *ODU, Journal of West African Studies*, 36, 115–138.

Anderson, R. C., & Pearson, P. D. (1984). *A schema-theoretic view of basic processes in reading comprehension*. In P. D. Pearson (Ed.), *Handbook of reading research* (pp. 255-291). New York: Longman.

Anisfeld, M., & Knapp, M. (1968). Association, synonymity, and directionality in false recognition. *Journal of Experimental Psychology*, 77, 171-179.

Atoye, R.O. (1994). Code-mixing, code-switching, borrowing and linguistic competence: Some conceptual fallacies. In B. Adediran (ed.), *Cultural Studies in Ife*. Ile-Ife: The Institute of Cultural Studies.

Atkinson, R. C., & Shiffrin, R. M. *Human memory : A proposed system and its control processes*. (1968). In K. W. Spence & J. T. Spence (Eds.), *The psychology of learning and motivation: Advances in research and theory* (Vol. 2). New York: Academic Press.

Ayeomoni, M. O. (2006). Code-switching and code-mixing: Style of language use in childhood in Yoruba speech community. *Nordic Journal of African Studies*, 15(1), 90–99.

Bartlett, F. C. (1932). *Remembering: a study in experimental and social psychology*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.

Baddeley, A. D. (1976). *The psychology of memory*. New York: Basic Books.

Belly, R. T. (1976). *Sociolinguistics: Goals, approaches and problems*. London: B.T. Batsford Ltd.

Bogaards, P., & Laufer, B. (Eds.) (2004). *Vocabulary in a second language: selection, acquisition and testing*. Benjamins, Amsterdam.

Bokamba, E. (1989). Are there syntactic constraints on code-mixing? *World Englishes*, 8(3).

Bower, G. H. (1967). *A multicomponent theory of the memory trace*. In K. W. Spence & J. T. Spence (Eds.), *The psychology of learning and motivation* (Vol. 1). New York: Academic Press.

Bransford, J. D., & Franks, J. J. (1971). The abstraction of linguistic ideas. *Cognitive Psychology*, 2, 231-250.

Brewer, W.F. and Nakamura, G.V. (1984). *The nature and function of schemas*. In R. S. Wyer, & T. K. Srull (Ed.), *Handbook of social cognition* (pp. 119-160) (Vol. 1), Hillsdale, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.

Bruce, D., & Murdock, B. B. (1968). Acoustic similarity effects on memory for paired associates. *Journal of Verbal Learning and Verbal Behaviour*, 7, 627-631.

Chepyshko, R., & Truscott, J. (2009). Semantic category effects in L2 vocabulary learning: A MOGUL perspective, *Journal of Applied Linguistics and Language Research*, 1(1).

Coady, J., & Huckin, T. (Eds.) (1997). *Second language vocabulary acquisition: A rationale for pedagogy*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.

Cohen, J. (1988). *Statistical power analysis for the behavioral sciences*. Hillsdale, NJ: Erlbaum.

Cooper, J. O., Heron, T. E., & Heward, W. L. (1987). *Applied behavior analysis*. Columbus, OH: Merrill/Prentice Hall.

Craik, F. I. M., & Lockhart, R. S. (1972). Levels of processing: A framework for memory research. *Journal of Verbal Learning and Verbal Behavior*, 11, 671-684.

Craik, F. I. M., & Tulving, E. (1975). Depth of processing and retention of words in episodic memory. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General*, 105, 268-294.

Creswell, J. W. & Creswell, J. D. (2017). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*. (4th ed.). Sage, Newbury Park.

Creswell, J. W. (2012). *Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research* (4th ed.). Boston, MA: Pearson.

Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2018). *Research design* (5th ed.). SAGE Publications.

Dale, H. C. A., & Baddeley, A. D. (1969). Acoustic similarity in long-term paired-associate learning. *Psychonomic Science*, 16, 209-211.

Dang, T. N. Y. (2020). Vietnamese non-English major EFL university students' receptive knowledge of the most frequent English words. *VNU J. Foreign Stud.*, 36, 1–11.

Erten, I. H., & Tekin, M. (2008). Effects of vocabulary acquisition of presenting new words in semantic sets versus semantically unrelated sets. *System*, 36(3), 407-422.

Eysenck, M. (1979). *Depth, elaboration, and distinctiveness*. In L. S. Cermak & F. I. M. Craik (Eds.). *Levels of processing in human memory*. (pp. 171-179). Hillsdale, N.J.: Erlbaum.

Fillmore C. J. & Atkins B. T. (1992). *Toward a frame-based lexicon: the semantics of RISK and its neighbors*. In A. Lehrer & E. F. Kittay (Eds.) (pp. 75-102). *Frames, fields, and contrasts*. Hillsdale, NJ: Erlbaum.

Fillmore, C.J. (1985). Semantic fields and semantic frames. *Quaderni di Semantica*, 6, 222–254.

Finkbeiner, M., & Nicol, J. (2003). Semantic category effects in second language word learning. *Applied Psycholinguistics*, 24, 369-383.

Gholami, J., & Khezrlou, S. (2014). Semantic and Thematic List Learning of Second Language Vocabulary. *The CATESOL Journal*, 25, 151-162.

Gopalakrishnan, V., Pang, C., & Kuo, C. C. J. (2009). Thematic clustering for topic identification in document collections. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 60(11), 2310-2326.

Hashemi, M. R., & Gowdasiaei, F. (2005). An attribute-treatment interaction study: Lexical-set versus semantically-unrelated vocabulary instruction. *RELC Journal*, 36(3), 341-361.

Hippner-Page T. (2000). Semantic clustering versus thematic clustering of English vocabulary words for second language instruction: Which method is more effective? *ERIC Document Reproduction Service*, ED445550.

Hornby, A. S. (2018). *Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary of Current English* (9th ed., pp. 586). Oxford University Press, Oxford.

Hoshino, Y. (2010). The categorical facilitation effects on L2 vocabulary learning in a classroom setting. *RELC Journal*, 41(3), 301- 312.

Hunt, R. R., & Elliot, J. M. (1980). The role of nonsemantic information in memory: Orthographic distinctiveness effects on retention. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General*, 109(1), 49–74. doi:10.1037/0096-3445.109.1.49

Hunt, R.R. & Mitchell, D.B. (1982). Independent effects of semantic and nonsemantic distinctiveness. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Learning, Memory, and Cognition*, 8, 81–87.

Hunt, R. R., & Mitchell, D. B. (1978). Specificity in non- semantic orienting tasks and distinctive memory traces. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Human Learning and Memory*, 4, 121-135.

Jacoby, L. L. (1975). Physical features vs. meaning: A difference in decay. *Memory & Cognition*, 3, 247-251.

Jacoby, L. L., & Craik, F. I. M. (1979). Effects of elaboration of processing at encoding and retrieval: Trace distinctiveness and recovery of initial context. In L. S. Cermak & F. I. M. Craik (Eds.), *Levels of processing in human memory*. Hillsdale, N.J.: Erlbaum.

Johnson-Laird, P. H. & Stevenson, R. (1970). Memory for syntax. *Nature*, 227, 442.

Johnston, C. D., & Jenkins, J. J. (1971). Two more incidental tasks that differentially affect associative clustering in recall. *Journal of Experimental Psychology*, 89, 92-95.

Khayef, E., & Khoshnevis, I. (2012). The effect of thematic versus semantic clustering of English vocabulary. *Journal of Basic and Applied Scientific Research*, 2(5), 5007-5016.

Kintsch, W., & Buschke, H. (1969). Homophones and synonyms in short-term memory. *Journal of Experimental Psychology*, 80, 403-407.

Markman, E.M. & Hutchinson, J.E. (1984). Children's sensitivity to constraints on word meaning: taxonomic versus thematic relations. *Cognitive Psychology*, 16, 1-27.

McCarthy, M., & O'Dell, F. (2017). *English vocabulary in use*. Cambridge University Press.

Mirjalili, F., Jabbari, A. A. & Rezai, M. J. (2012). The effect of semantic and thematic clustering of words on Iranians vocabulary learning. *American International Journal of Contemporary Research*, 2(2), 214-222.

Morikawa, Y. (1955). Studies in paired associates learning: forward-backward recall gradient. *Japanese Journal of Psychology*, 26, 156-171.

Nation (2006). How large a vocabulary is needed for reading and listening?, *The Canadian Modern Language Review*, 63(1), 59-82.

Nguyen, T. M. H. & Webb, S. (2017). Examining second language receptive knowledge of collocation and factors that affect learning. *Lang. Teach. Res.*, 21, 298–320.

Nelson, D. L. (1979). Remembering pictures and words: Appearance, significance, and name. In L. S. Cermak & F. I. M. Craik (Eds.). *Levels of processing in human memory*. Hillsdale, N.J.: Erlbaum.

Nelson, D. L., & Borden, R. C. (1973). Effect of "meaning" of the processing of the phonetic features of words. *Journal of Experimental Psychology*, 101, 373-375.

Nelson, D. L., & Brooks, D. H. (1973). Independence of phonetic and imaginal features. *Journal of Experimental Psychology*, 97, 1-7.

Nelson, D. L., & Brooks, D. H. (1974). Relative effectiveness of rhymes and synonyms as retrieval cues. *Journal of Experimental Psychology*, 102, 503-507.

Nelson, D. L., Brooks, D. H., & Borden, R. C. (1974). The effects of formal similarity: Phonetic, graphic or both? *Journal of Experimental Psychology*, 103, 91-96.

Nelson, D. L., Brooks, D. H., & Fosselman, J. R. (1972). Words as sets of features: Processing phonological cues. *Journal of Experimental Psychology*, 92, 305-312.

Nelson, D. L., Reed, V. S., & McEvoy, C. L. (1977). Learning to order pictures and words: A model of sensory and semantic encoding. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Human Learning and Memory*, 3, 485-497.

Nelson, D. L., Wheeler, J. W., & Brooks, D. H. (1976). Meaning and the elimination of sensory interference. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Human Learning and Memory*, 2, 95-102.

Neuman, S. G., & McCormick, S. (Eds.) (1995). *Single-subject experimental research: Applications for literacy*. Newark, DE: International Reading Association.

Nock, M. K., Michel, B. D. & Photos, V. I. (2007). *Single-Case Research Designs*. Sage Publishing.

Poling, A., & Grosset, D. (1986). *Basic research designs in applied behavior analysis*. In A. Poling & R. Fuque (Eds.), *Research methods in applied behavior analysis: Issues and advances* (pp. 7–27). New York: Plenum.

Peterson, R.A. (1994). “A Meta-analysis of Cronbach’s coefficient alpha”. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 21(2), 381-391, <https://doi.org/10.1086/209405>

Read, J. (2000). *Assessing Vocabulary*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.

Richards, J. C. & Renandya, W. A. (2002). *Methodology in language teaching: An anthology of current practice*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.

Rahimi, H. (2014). The effect of method of vocabulary presentation (code-mixing, thematic clustering, and contextualization) on L2 vocabulary recognition and production. *Procedia: Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 98, 1475–1484.

Rahmati, H. & Helmiyadi, H. (2021). The analysis of using thematic vocabulary cards in increasing the students' English vocabulary. *Getsempena English Education Journal*, 8(1), 110-122. <https://doi.org/10.46244/geej.v8i1.1284>

Romero, Y. (2009). Promoting Language Learning through a Thematic Vocabulary-Based Syllabus in Different Grades. *Latin American Journal of Content & Language Integrated Learning*, 2(1).

Sarioğlu, M. & Yıldırım, Ö. (2018). The effects of clustering new words in semantic, thematic or unrelated sets in teaching vocabulary to EFL learners. *Abant İzzet Baysal Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 18(2), 1064-1085.

Sachs, J. S. (1967). Recognition memory for syntactic and semantic aspects of connected discourse. *Perception & Psychophysiks*, 2, 437-442.

Schulman, A. I. (1974). Memory for words recently classified. *Memory & Cognition*, 2, 47-52.

Smiley, S. S., & Brown, A. L. (1979) Conceptual preference for thematic or taxonomic relations: A nonmonotonic age trend from preschool to old age. *Journal of Experimental Child Psychology*, 28, 249-257.

Smith, E. E., Adams, N. E., & Schorr, D. (1978). Fact retrieval and the paradox of interference. *Cognitive Psychology*, 10(4), 438-464. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-0285\(78\)90007-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-0285(78)90007-5)

Stein, B. S. (1978). Depth of processing reexamined: The effects of the precision of encoding and test appropriateness. *Journal of Verbal Learning and Verbal Behavior*, 17, 165-174.

Tinkham, T. (1993). The effect of semantic clustering on the learning of second language vocabulary. *System*, 21(3), 371-380.

Tinkham, T. (1997). The effects of semantic and thematic clustering on the learning of second language vocabulary. *Second Language Research*, 13(2), 138-163.

Tran, H. Q. (2013). Figurative idiomatic competence: An analysis of EFL learners in Vietnam. *Lang. Educ. Asia*, 4, 23–38.

Tracey, D. H., & Morrow, L. M. (2006). *Lenses on reading: an introduction to theories and models*. New York: Guilford Press.

Tagashira, K., Kida, S., & Hoshino, Y. (2010). Hot or gelid? The influence of L1 translation familiarity on the interference effects in foreign language vocabulary learning. *System*, 38(3), 412–421. doi:10.1016/j.system.2010.03.015

Underwood, B. J. (1969). Attributes of memory. *Psychological Review*, 76, 559-573.

Vu, D. V. & Peters, E. (2021). Vocabulary in English language learning, teaching, and testing in Vietnam: A Review. *Educ. Sci.*, *11*, 563. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci11090563>

Vu, D. V. & Nguyen, N. C. (2019). An assessment of vocabulary knowledge of Vietnamese EFL learners. *Proceedings of the 20th English in South-East Asia Conference: Singapore, 6-7 December 2019*. National Institute of Education, Nanyang Technological University: Singapore.

Walsh, D. A., & Jenkins, J. J. (1973). Effects of orienting tasks on free recall in incidental learning: "Difficulty," "effort," and "process" explanations. *Journal of Verbal Learning and Verbal Behavior*, *12*, 481-488.

Waring, R. (1997). The negative effects of learning words in semantic sets: A replication. *System*, *25*(2), 261-274.

Willis, D. (1990). *The lexical syllabus*. London: Collins.

Waugh, N. C, & Norman, D. A. (1965). Primary memory. *Psychological Review*, *72*, 89-104.

Zargosh, M., Karbalaeei, A., & Afraz, S. (2013). The effect of thematic clustering on enhancing monolingual and bilingual EFL learners' vocabulary acquisition. *European Online Journal of Natural and Social Sciences* 2013, *2*(2), 109-121.

Zarei, A. A., & Adami, S. (2013). The effects of semantic mapping, thematic clustering, and notebook keeping on L2 vocabulary recognition and production. *Journal on English Language Teaching*, 3(2), 17-27.

Zarei, A. A., & Arasteh, T. S. (2011). The effects of code-mixing, thematic clustering, and contextualization on L2 vocabulary recognition and production. *Journal of Language and Culture*, 2(6), 96-102.

Zoltán, D. (2006). *Research methods in applied linguistics: quantitative, qualitative and mixed methodologies*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

APPENDICES

Appendix A

Declaration and Agreement of Collaboration

Ho Chi Minh City, March 1st, 2023

I am Ngo Nhat Thanh Tra, currently an IELTS Teacher of Pre-Intermediate level at Weset English Center.

As previously reaching approval and agreement by Weset English Center, I hereby given the privileges to conduct research on students learning English at the centre, particularly students of the three classes that I am in charge of: IE-Pre202212-246-1-1, IE-Pre202211-246-2-2 and IE-Pre202303-357-1.

The research is conducted by prior reaching consent by the students in charge (hereby referred to as Participant) and on the basis of remain separate and independent on the students' result at the centre. All the data collected are used solely for the purpose of conducting my graduation thesis at Ho Chi Minh City University of Law, and the students' information remained confidential thereof.

The participants hereby understand that they are voluntarily attending the research, and that they will not receive any privileges or indemnities regarding their final results at the centre by attending this research. They also understand that all of their personal information will be kept in confidential.

I hereby committed to understand and be responsible for the above information.

Ngo Nhat Thanh Tra

Appendix B

Vocabulary Bank

Observing others (Unit 19): impetuous; impulsive; pushy; taciturn; disdainful; gullible; obstinate; unscrupulous; haughty; aloof

Language of law (Unit 47): embezzlement; harassment; insider trading; joyriding; perjury; indictable; discretionary; infringe; verdict; abrogate

Colour (Unit 68): crimson; turquoise; chestnut; auburn; fluorescent; mousy; mauve; reddish; emerald; amber

Difficulties, dilemmas and hitches (Unit 72): stumbling; abstruse; arduous; convoluted; wayward; ordeal; glitch; affliction; tribulation; grueling

Permission and prohibition (Unit 75) and Complaining and protesting (Unit 76): accede; acquiesce; assent; condone; endorse; veto; clamp down; sanction; remonstrate; grouse

Diet, sport and fitness (Unit 58) and Health and illness 3 (Unit 57): plaque; buffer; offal; banish; gut; artery; stool; ulcer; ail; jaundiced

Birth and death (Unit 20): womb; Caesarean section; placenta; uterus; ectopic pregnancy; conceived; fertility drugs; foetus; fallopian tubes; fortitude

The plastic arts (Unit 26): philistinism; detractor; Tate Modern; Renaissance; fad; cubist; surrealist; deem; inured to; Impressionism

Travel and accommodation (Unit 31): apex; berth; upper deck; restriction; self-catering; chalet; inn; half board; full board; charter

Authorities (Unit 40): landing card; sniffer dog; political asylum; fixed penalty; breathalyser; surveillance; search warrant; traffic wardens; clear custom; refugee

History (Unit 44): depose; proclaim; monarchy; laws of succession; predecessor; regent; seize; corrupt; reign; usurp power

British politics (Unit 46): legislation; constituent; Institute of Director; Chancellor of the Exchequer; petition; concession; Member of Parliament; assiduously; annual climax; parliament

Appendix C

Tests

Non-Treatment 01

1. He's so [1], I wish he would consider things first.
2. [2]: stealing money that is in your care or belongs to an organization that you work for
3. [3]: strong deep red
4. [4]: something that prevents free action, progress or movement
5. The Prime Minister had [5] to demands to release secret documents about the recent war.
6. [6]: unwanted substance that forms on the surface of the arteries
7. His [7] generosity led him to give away most of his money
8. [8]: making a person feel anxious and unhappy
9. [9]: greenish blue, used about fabrics, paint, sea, etc. but not usually eyes
10. [10]: difficult to understand

Non-Treatment 02

1. She's so [1], it's typical of her to demand an interview for the new job.
2. [2]: illegal buying and selling of shares by someone who has specialist knowledge of a company
3. [3] a deep reddish brown, used about hair and horses
4. [4]: difficult, tiring, needing much effort
5. The Foreign Minister [5] in the plan to restrict imports from certain countries.
6. [6]: something/someone that helps protect from harm.
7. I thought he was rather [7] when I first met him. He hardly spoke.
8. [8]: lying under oath.
9. [9]: a red-brown colour, usually used about hair

10. [10]: unreasonably long and hard to follow

Non-Treatment 03

1. Britain had [1] to a proposal to enlarge the EU.
2. [2]: organs from inside animals which are eaten as food (brains, heart, kidneys, liver)
3. She's always been [3] of people who haven't been to college.
4. [4]: for which you can be charged as a serious crime that needs a trial by jury
5. [5]: very bright colour
6. [6]: changeable, selfish and/or hard to control
7. The judge [7] the use of reasonable force by the police officers who arrested the man.
8. [8]: to make somebody/something go away; to get rid of somebody/something.
9. Telephone sales people often take advantage of [9] people.
10. [10]: decided according to the judgement of a person in authority about what is necessary in each particular situation; not decided by rules

Non-Treatment 04

1. [1]: a light not very interesting brown, used only about hair
2. [2]: severe experience, which is very difficult, painful or tiring
3. The cabinet has [3] a proposal to change the way universities are funded and managed.
4. [4]: tubes that carry food from the stomach.
5. You are so [5] and pig-headed! Why don't you listen when people give you good advice?
6. [6]: to break a law or rule
7. [7]: pale purple
8. [8]: a technical problem of some kind
9. The president had [9] the plan to open membership of the club to the public.

10. [10]: any of the tubes that carry blood from the heart to other parts of the body.

Non-Treatment 05

1. He's quite an [1] character; I should be careful if I were you.
2. [2]: an official judgement made in court or at an inquest
3. [3]: partly red
4. [4]: pain and difficulty or something that causes it
5. The government has decided to [5] on illegal immigration.
6. [6]: a piece of solid waste from your body.
7. My aunt Annie can be very [7] and disdainful, but she's lovely really.
8. [8]: driving around for enjoyment in a car you have stolen
9. [9]: bright green in colour
10. [10]: great trouble, difficulty or mental pain

Non-Treatment 06

1. Trade [1] were imposed against any country that refused to sign the agreement.
2. [2]: painful infected area on the skin or inside your body.
3. Barbara tends to be rather [3], I don't know if she's just shy.
4. [4]: to officially end a law, an agreement, etc.
5. [5]: yellow-brown in colour
6. [6]: extremely tiring and difficult
7. They [7] with the official about the decision.
8. [8]: to cause problems for somebody/something.
9. [9]: to complain about somebody/something in a way that other people find annoying.
10. [10]: not expecting somebody/something to be good or useful, especially because of experiences that you have had in the past.

Treatment 01

Doctors praised the [1] of a mother yesterday who made medical history when she gave birth to triplets, one of whom had grown outside her [2]. The surgeons delivered the triplets by [3] last Friday after it was discovered that one of the babies had created its own [4] - tissue joining the [5] - outside the womb, putting the life of the mother at risk. Doctors had discovered that the mother was expecting triplets earlier in the pregnancy but it was not until the 28th week that they realized that Ronan had developed outside the [6] and was the result of [7], i.e when the egg develops outside the womb in the [8], which link the ovaries the womb. The mother had [9] naturally and was not taking any [10]. The majority of ectopic pregnancies result in termination.

Treatment 02

You have heard it so often, that all those modern artists are only pulling the wool over the public's eyes, and it is easy to laugh, in a superior kind of way, both at the more extreme examples of contemporary art and at the apparent [1] of its [2].

The current enthusiasm for modern art - there are more people visiting [3] every week than there were people in Florence at the height of the [4] - appears to be more than a [5]. If people got nothing from what they see there, they would vote with their feet. At the end of the 19th century a lot of people had problems with [6], and, later, when confronted with [7] paintings, the gallery-going public had problems with those too. The [8] were often [9], but liking surrealism is perfectly same and acceptable, and it appears everywhere, from posters to advertising campaigns. As a result, we are all now more visually literate than before, more immune to shocks, [10] surprises.

Treatment 03

The scheduled flight is a normal, regular flight; a [1] flight is a special flight taking a group of people. usually to the same holiday destination. [2] fares normally

have to be booked a fixed number of days in advance and they offer value for money. Budget fares are usually cheaper but may have some [3] and are usually non-refundable or if you cancel, you may have to pay a cancellation fee.

When you go sea travel, you may decide to book a [4] in a shared cabin, or to have a single or double cabin. For more money, you can often get a deluxe cabin, perhaps on the [5] - the highest part of the ship, which is often bigger and more comfortable.

Some people prefer hotels. Others prefer [6] - where you do your own cooking - accommodation, such as a holiday apartment or [7] - small cottage or cabin especially built for holiday-makers. In Britain and Ireland, guests houses and [8] - similar to pubs, also offering accommodation - offer good accommodation which is often cheaper than hotels, and there are many private homes offering bed-and-breakfast. Some types of accommodation offer [9] (usually breakfast and one other meal) or [10].

Treatment 04

On arrival in most countries as a foreigner you have to show your passport, a [1] and often a customs declaration form. You may need a visa and a vaccination certificate depending on the entry restrictions. Customs carry out spot checks/randoms checks on people's luggage. They use [2] to search for drugs and explosives. In most cases, you have to [3] at the port of entry. Genuine [4] may try to seek [5]. Customs officers also look out for illegal immigrants, some of whom may be economic migrants.

For some traffic offenses you have to pay a [6], and this may be an on-the-spot-fine. Parking tickets for illegal parking are issued by police and/or [7].

If there has been an accident, the police may ask drivers to take a [8] test and to make a statement at a police station.

Police have limited stop-and-search powers. [9] cameras operate in many public areas.

A police officer cannot normally enter your home against your wishes without a [10].

Treatment 05

Lord Acton said, 'All power corrupts but absolute power [1] absolutely? Historically, power in Britain rests with the [2]. Kings and queens succeed one another to the throne according to the [3] A new monarch accedes to the throne as soon as his or her [4] dies. The eldest son of the current monarch is the heir apparent with other close relatives said to be, say, second, third or fourth in line to the throne. If the eldest son is too young to [5], then a [6] may take his place until he reaches a suitable age. There have been times in history when a pretender has laid claim to the throne, saying that it should rightfully belong to him, rather than to the person [7] king. In other words, he is trying to [8] that king and to [9] power for himself. His opponents would say that such a pretender is trying to [10]. If he succeeds, then the person whose place he takes can be said to fall from power. A person who does not use power well can be said to abuse power.

Treatment 06

Behind the public debates of [1], the hidden pressures on government influence [2] much more than speeches. Growing numbers of [3] are themselves well-paid to represent commercial or special interests, sometimes more [4] than their own [5]. But the most powerful lobbies, like the big corporations or the [6] do not bother much about Members: they can go straight to ministers and civil servants. Lobbyists

reach their [7] when the [8] is preparing his annual budget and receives [9] from business interests pressing for tax [10].

Appendix D

Pre-Interview Questions

1. Can you describe the way you normally learn vocabulary?
2. What do you think about learning vocabulary in a random list?
3. What do you think about learning vocabulary by theme?

Appendix E

Post-Interview Questions

1. How do you feel about the first two week of the experiments? Is it easy or difficult to learn new words by this way, compared to others?
2. How do you feed about the last two week of the experiment? Is it easy or difficult to learn new words by this way, compared to others?
3. Which one do you prefer?
4. Which one is more effective for you?
5. If you can suggest your school to choose either method, what should you suggest, either or both?